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Evaluation 1 of "Existential Risk and Growth"

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Executive Summary:

Authors find: (1) existential risk follows an inverted-u shape in both technology level and over time (2), technological accelerations reduce cumulative existential danger. These findings are novel and important, implying a “time of perils” after which safety is (asymptotically) assured. Two critiques: (1) the representative agent of the model is neither a normative goal nor a positive prediction, making implications nebulous (2) omission of savings from the model eliminates an alternate mechanism for intertemporal consumption smoothing

Full Review

I thank the editors of The Unjournal for the invitation to review this provocative and hopeful paper for your exciting new journal.

Determining whether and when anthropocentric existential risks will actually bite is a difficult question for several reasons. One reason is the difficulty in estimating the ‘existential risk damage function’. Another is human agency - depending on our incentives we might consciously work to reduce risk and increase safety.

This paper is focused on the second question. It investigates the dynamics of economic growth existential risk, assuming simple but plausible analytic forms for output, existential danger, and representative agent utility. It highlights that, under the assumption that risk aversion is strong: (1) existential risk follows an inverted-u shape in both technology level and over time (2), technological accelerations reduce cumulative existential danger.

I found the paper well written and generally easy to follow. I especially appreciated the way that section 2 previewed the main results in a mathematically accessible way. The paper anticipated my desire to think about a less risk averse planner in section 3.3.4, and a humble discussion of parameter selection in appendix A1. I will say I found section 4 somewhat extraneous -- although I appreciated the intuitive result that if \dot{A} directly and immediately increases danger, with consumption benefits lagging, that \dot{A} increases can be dangerous.

I do have some critiques of some aspects of the model and its discussion, but overall I find it to make an important contribution to our understanding of the relationship between economic growth and existential risk.

Why do we care about this particular representative agent? Distinguishing the normative and positive content of the model.

From the perspective of any potential optimizing representative agent, an increase in A is always a good thing for welfare (by $\beta > \alpha$). The key words being “from the perspective of”. The paper’s implicit normative

framing is: An existential catastrophe would be exceedingly bad and we should prefer decision rules that don't produce it. In other words, the paper doesn't take the goals of the representative agent as necessarily normative.

On the other hand, the paper only weakly argues that the representative agent is anything like a positive model of how AI risk decisions will be made in the real world. While the argument that the wealth induced by AI will decrease the marginal propensity of consumption and induce substitution into safety is a generally robust one, the details of "who's marginal propensity to consume"¹ is left open -- is this the MPC of the median voter in the US? Of the President? Of the average person globally? The same question holds for the discount rate, which is also heterogenous. Similarly, "Race" dynamics are likely to be important between leading labs and countries (Aschenbrenner, 2024), which would also be hard to model with a single representative agent. This disconnect between the representative agent and the real world is worse than the one in Jones (2016), which has a similar model, but is concerned with individual mortality.

I think the paper could do a better job explaining why these particular growth/risk paths are interesting if they are neither a positive prediction nor a normative imperative. I think the authors would say that the representative agent represents a sort of "idealized international institution" that a sane hegemon would plausibly sign up the world for (perhaps in the wake of a successful "The Project" (Aschenbrenner, 2024)).

Whether or not that's the case, in follow-up work it might be useful to evaluate or contextualize the social planner analyzed according to other explicit social welfare functions that might be normatively endorsed. For example:

- A "hard" utilitarian might choose a gamma with perfect substitution between consumption across periods -- so no decreasing marginal product of consumption -- and a discount rate equal to the unpreventable existential risk rate
 - This agent would view the representative agent as much too conservative and risk averse
- An agent who is only trying to minimize existential risk, perhaps conditional on some minimum consumption level
 - This agent would view the representative agent as much too incautious

Is Leaving Capital Out of the Model Harmless?

A second question I have about the modeling is how harmless the assumption of ignoring capital accumulation is. I have one concern and one comment related to this.

The concern is that some of the results may be driven by the fact that "decreasing safety" is the only way to increase immediate consumption in the model. In real life, we also have the choice of reducing the saving rate. This additional mechanism might weaken the papers' findings: a shock to \dot{A} increases future wealth in a

way that only incentivizes more safety in the current model. In a more general model with savings, an increase in \dot{A} could instead lead to dissaving in the short term to smooth consumption between periods, and less of an increase in safety spending. (I could also see it pushing in the opposite direction, making future existence more valuable because of the ability to intertemporally substitute with savings).

A more minor point is that the capital-labor distinction is one of the major ways that heterogeneity in preferences complicates the representative agent framework. The advance of AI is likely to increase the share of income paid to capital and reduce the share paid to labor, as well as redistributing income between types of workers. Likely, those who own capital may have lower risk tolerances than those who provide labor (they are both richer, and may also be more patient in general -- although a lifetime savings model would suggest, alternatively, that the richest agents might be on the verge of retirement and relatively impatient). This is just one mechanism by which technology may itself shape the preferences of a representative agent, but I think an important one (Benzell et al 2023).

Minor Comments:

The authors argue that historical anthropocentric existential safety expenditure has been near 0. I question this. If I view my enemy as completely alien to my values, wouldn't military spending count? One historical theory I have in mind is that the Habsburg Empire intentionally slowed economic growth and increased military spending to avoid a socialist revolution. An even older example could be the prophecies of Jeremiah and similar prophets who connected contemporary decadence and evil (the high consumption of the ruling class?) to a coming disaster, and recommended shifting resources to ameliorating religious rituals.

While this paper draws on Jones (2016) it does so much less than the previous draft, and does a much better job highlighting innovations vs. replicating that paper. Relative to Jones (2024) this paper is less precise in distinguishing the effects of degrees of risk aversion, but has richer dynamics. My critiques mostly apply to Jones (2024) as well.

References

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Footnotes

1. A small complementary point is that the parameterization of $\gamma < 1$ makes sense at an individual level, but is much too risk averse from a social welfare perspective. It is contrary to the ordinary intuition that two happy flourishing people is roughly twice as good as one happy flourishing person -- i.e. aggregate utility is linear in individual utility. I understand this argument starts to go in a repugnant conclusion direction, and the authors are assuming a fixed exogenous population growth rate, but it's an illustration of how γ as an individual behavior parameter might be different than γ as a social welfare function parameter. [↵](#)